

IPBES VA Chapter 4. Systematic review on valuation uptake / IPBES values assessment (4.4)

Code: IPBES_VA_4.4

Versioning 01: (21.10.2020)

Versioning 02: (28.04.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4391335

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Description

The IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment describes that *Chapter 4* should address values and valuation in relation to decision-making and policymaking at different levels and in different contexts, placing special importance on those methods that have been uptaken by decision-making. In this context a review of empirical scientific literature was conducted to identify causes for lacking uptake (blindspots) and facilitators of best-practice uptake of valuation (brightspots).

Process overview

Protocol:

Stage 1. Corpus identification¹

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review
- **Search language:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** 6 May 2020
- **Search terms:** Full set of search terms can be found in **(R1)**. The period of publication year was defined as going from January 1981 - March 2020.
- **Sample extracted (A):** 79040 papers
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - (AU) Authors
 - (TI) Title
 - (SO) Journal
 - (JI) ISO Source Abbreviation
 - (AB) Abstract
 - (DE) Author keywords
 - (ID) Keywords Plus®
 - (LA) Language
 - (DT) Document type
 - (DT2) Document type
 - (TC) Web of Science core collection times cited count
 - (C1) Author address
 - (DI) Digital object identifier
 - (PA) Publisher Address
 - (AR) Article number
 - (BE) Editors
 - (FU) Funding (FU)
 - (FX) Funding text
 - (BN) International standard book number (ISBN)
 - (SN) International standard serial number (ISSN)
 - (PN) Part number
 - (PP) Pages
 - (PU) Publisher
 - (VL) Volume
 - (PY) Year published
 - (UT) Accession number
 - (NR) Cited reference count
 - (SC) Research areas
 - (U2) Usage count (since 2013)
 - (WC) Web of Science categories
 - (EM) E-mail Address
 - (SE) Book series title
 - (GA) Document delivery number
 - (BO) Book title

¹ The description of this stage is parallel to the first section of the DMRs the Systematic PCIV (Principles, Criteria, Indicators, Verifiers) review on valuation methods (10.5281/zenodo.4404678) and Valuation Atlas (10.5281/zenodo.6468906). The corpus obtained was used for the three reviews which inform both Chapter 3 and Chapter 4.

- (RP) Reprint address
- (DB) Database
- (CR) Cited references

Treatment applied: Geographical names extraction. The country names were extracted from fields TI, AB, DE, ID, CI, FU, FX in document (A). They were grouped as (TI, AB, DE, ID) and (CI,FU,FX). Then, they were added to the same document with their ISO 3 codes (<https://www.iso.org/iso-3166-country-codes.html>) as fields:

- CountryName_TI_AB_DE_ID
- CountryName_CI_FU_FX CI & FU & FX

Treatment applied: IPBES regions and subregions. The country names were later merged by IPBES regions and subregions. IPBES regions and subregions obtained from <https://zenodo.org/record/3928281> These were added to document (A) in fields:

- Region_TI_AB_DE_ID
- Region_CI_FU_FX
- Subregion_TI_AB_DE_ID
- Subregion_CI_FU_FX

Treatment applied: Selection of papers for review had to do with papers including a combination of search terms in the NATURE & DIVERSITY lists, the VALUE lists and the METHODS list in the titles, keywords or abstracts of the paper. Fields in (A) indicating presence or absence of these terms are:

- TS1
- TS2
- TS3
- ...
- TS27

Location and format of the data (A): IPBES_VA_4.4_06.05.2020_(A).csv

Stage 2. Selection of a sample of studies based on method family identified for Chapter 4

Treatment applied: Considering the search terms below (Table 1), a random stratified sample was conducted. Strata were defined by the following search term strata (ID numbers from the first column in Table 1): 20, 21, 22 and 23. That is, all the studies that had search terms for values (ID 1), methods (ID 5), decision-making (ID 12) and Nature_Biodiversity (ID 16) occurring with (AND) method family specific keywords in (ID 8), (ID 9), (ID 10) and (ID 11)

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Definition of the sample of papers to be used in Chapter 4
- **Search language:** English
- **Exact search date:** 10 June 2020
- **Search terms:**

Table 1. List of search terms for defining sample for Chapter 4

ID	Name	TS
1	Values = #1 #2 OR #3 OR #4	TS=(wellbeing OR welfare OR well-being OR utilit* OR "quality of life" OR "willingness-to-pay" OR "willingness to pay" OR WTP OR "willingness-to-accept" OR WTA OR "willingness to accept" OR "human-nature relat*" OR "society-nature relat*" OR "ecosystem servi*" OR "environmental servi*" OR "intrinsic valu*" OR "relational valu*" OR "cultural valu*" OR "instrumental valu*" OR "option valu*" OR "insurance valu*" OR "bequest valu*" OR "indirect valu*" OR "existence valu*" OR "non-use valu*" OR "direct use valu*" OR biocentrism OR "ecosystem function*" OR "ecosystem process*" OR "ecological resilience" OR "genetic diversity" OR "functional diversity" OR "taxonomic diversity" OR "phylogenetic diversity" OR "embodied energy" OR "genetic resource*" OR "Human Appropriation of Net Primary Production" OR HANPP OR "carbon footprint" OR "water

		<p>footprint" OR "environmental footprint" OR "ecological footprint" OR "habitat quality" OR "habitat for" OR "biodiversity" OR "regulating service*" OR "climate regulation" OR "regulation of water*" OR "pollination" OR "biological control" OR "water quality" OR "air quality" OR "flood control" OR "provisioning service*" OR "cultural service*" OR "ecotourism" OR "ascribed valu*" OR "held valu*" OR "psychological benefits" OR "food security" OR "water security" OR "energy security" OR "social-ecological resilience" OR "social resilience" OR "social sustainability" OR "economic sustainability" OR "ecological sustainability" OR "biocultural diversity" OR "diversity of * options" OR "sense of place" OR "sense of community" OR "intra-generational equity" OR "inter-generational equity" OR "environmental justice" OR "mental health" OR "physical health" OR "economic valu*" OR "social valu*" OR "socio-cultural val*" OR "happiness" OR "recreation*" OR "amenity" OR "outdoor" OR "non-timber product*" OR "fuelwood" OR "charcoal" OR "subsistence" OR "timber" OR "natures contributions to people" OR "benefit* to people" OR "benefit* to humans" OR "NCP" OR "ecosystem service*" OR "disservice" OR "well being" OR "income" OR "poverty" OR "human well*" OR "nutrition" OR "livelihood*" OR "security" OR "vulnerab*" OR "social capital" OR "human capital" OR "asset*" OR "social welfare" OR "poor communit*" OR "poor people" OR "indigenous people*" OR "well living" OR "living standard*" OR "life satisfaction" OR "prosperity" OR "progress" OR "needs fulfillment" OR "development" OR "empowerment" OR "capabilit*" OR "happiness" OR "nutrition* intake" OR "carbon sequestration" OR "sovereignty" OR "kinship" OR "reciprocity" OR "altruism" OR "altruistic" OR "shared valu*" OR "spiritual valu*" OR "religious valu*" OR "stewardship" OR "rights of nature" OR "Mother Earth")</p>
2	VALUES_INSTRUMENTAL	<p>TS=(wellbeing OR welfare OR well-being OR utilit* OR "willingness-to-pay" OR "willingness to pay" OR WTP OR "willingness-to-accept" OR WTA OR "willingness to accept" OR "ecosystem service" OR "instrumental valu*" OR "option valu*" OR "insurance valu*" OR "indirect valu*" OR "existence valu*" OR "non-use valu*" OR "direct use val*" OR "regulating service*" OR "climate regulation" OR "regulation of climate" OR "regulation of water*" OR "pollination" OR "biological control" OR "medicinal resource*" OR "water quality" OR "air quality" OR "flood control" OR "provisioning service*" OR "cultural service*" OR "ecotourism" OR "ascribed valu*" OR "food security" OR "water security" OR "energy security" OR "economic sustainability" OR "diversity of * options" OR "economic valu*" OR "happiness" OR "recreation*" OR "amenity" OR "outdoor" OR "non-timber product*" OR "fuelwood" OR "charcoal" OR "subsistence" OR "timber" OR "natures contributions to people" OR "benefit* to people" OR "benefit* to humans" OR "NCP" OR "ecosystem service*" OR "disservice" OR "well being" OR "income" OR "poverty" OR "human well*" OR "nutrition" OR "livelihood*" OR "security" OR "vulnerab*" OR "human capital" OR "asset*" OR "social welfare" OR "poor communit*" OR "poor people" OR "well living" OR "living standard*" OR "life satisfaction" OR "prosperity" OR "progress" OR "needs fulfillment" OR "development" OR "happiness" OR "nutrition* intake" OR "carbon sequestration")</p>
3	VALUES_INTRINSIC	<p>TS=("intrinsic valu*" OR "biocentrism" OR "ecosystem function*" OR "ecosystem process*" OR "ecological resilience" OR "genetic diversity" OR "functional diversity" OR "taxonomic diversity" OR "phylogenetic diversity" OR "embodied energy" OR "genetic resource*" OR "Human Appropriation of Net Primary Production" OR "HANPP" OR "carbon footprint" OR "water footprint" OR "environmental footprint" OR "ecological footprint" OR "habitat quality" OR "habitat for" OR "biodiversity" OR "ecological sustainability" OR "Mother Earth" OR "held valu*")</p>
4	VALUES_RELATIONAL	<p>TS=("quality of life" OR "human-nature relat*" OR "society-nature relat*" OR "relational valu*" OR "cultural valu*" OR "psychological benefits" OR "social-ecological resilience" OR "social resilience" OR "social sustainability" OR "biocultural diversity" OR "sense of place" OR "sense of community" OR "intra-generational equity" OR "inter-generational equity" OR "environmental justice" OR "mental health" OR "physical health" OR "social valu*" OR "socio-cultural val*" "social capital" OR "indigenous people*" OR "empowerment" OR "capabilit*" OR "sovereignty" OR "kinship" OR "reciprocity" OR "altruism" OR "bequest valu*")</p>
5	METHODS = #5 = #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11	<p>TS = (Valuation OR WTP OR "willingness to pay" OR "willingness to accept" OR WTA OR "preference assessment" OR "preference*" OR "benefit transfer*" OR "value transfer*" OR "non-monetary valuation" OR "monetary valuation" OR "elicitation method*" OR "value elicitation" OR PA-BAT OR "Trade-offs" OR "discourse analysis" OR "stakeholder workshop*" OR "interview*" OR "questionnaire*" OR "mental model*" OR "focus group*" OR "concept mapping" OR "Q methodology" OR "Q-methodology" OR "Q study" OR "Q-study" OR "bayesian belief network*" OR BN OR BBN OR "participatory GIS" OR "PPGIS" OR "PGIS" OR "narrative method*" OR "narrative approach*" OR ARIES OR "InVEST model*" OR "biophysical model*" OR "bio-physical model*" OR "biophysical valu*" OR "bio-physical valu*" OR "global environmental flow" OR Mapnat OR "MARKAN" OR "MEB" OR "Ecosystem service map*" OR "ES map*" OR "Ecological importance" OR "Spatial proxy model*" OR ESTIMAP OR GISGAME OR "Cultural Health Index" OR "Environmental importance" OR "POLYSCAPE" OR "ecosystem service quantification" OR "ES quantification" OR "ecosystem service modeling" OR "ES modeling" OR "service providing unit" OR "ecosystem service supply" OR "ES supply" OR "ecosystem service delivery" OR "ES delivery" OR "species richness" OR "biodiversity index" OR "species diversity" OR "ecosystem accounting" OR "contingent valuation" OR "choice experiment*" OR "conjoint analysis" OR "random utility" OR "RUM" OR "Marginal Utility" OR "Lancasters Characteristics demand theory" OR "Marginal rate of substitution" OR "choice model" OR "stated preferences" OR "deliberative valuation" OR "role playing game*" OR "social assessment for protected areas" OR "socio-cultural valuation" OR "expert * elicitation" OR "Afrocentric metho*" OR "Biocultural Methods" OR SAPA OR "participatory mapping" OR "social importance" OR "socio-economic importance" OR "socio-cultural importance" OR "social preferences" OR "Hypothetical policy scenario" OR "Willingness to pay" OR "Willingness to accept" OR "Compensation" OR "Nonmarket valuation survey" OR "Individual welfare change" OR "Equivalent variation of welfare" OR "Compensatory variation of welfare" OR "Multiattribute model*" OR "Multi-attribute model" OR "Discrete choice modelling" OR "Final mixture model" OR "Latent Class Model" OR "LCM" OR "Random Parameter Logit Model" OR RPLM OR "Mixed Logit Model" OR "alternative specific conditional logit" OR "hedonic" OR "travel cost" OR "cost-based" OR "cost-effectiveness" OR "production function" OR "shadow price*" OR "Health valuation" OR "Photo Elicitation" OR "Photo-Elicitation" OR "replacement cost*" OR "averting behavior" OR "economic importance" OR "livelihood assess*" OR "market price*" OR "market valu*" OR "time use" OR "mitigating cost*" OR "preventive expenditure*" OR "cost of illness" OR "participant observation" OR "observe behavior" OR "observe practice*" OR "ritua*" OR "ceremon*" OR "cost-benefit" OR "cost benefit" OR "benefit cost" OR "benefit-cost" OR "MCA" OR "multicriteria analysis" OR "MCDA" OR "multicriteria decision analysis" OR "integrated valuation" OR "deliberative decision making" OR "business accounting" OR "corporate accounting" OR "profit and loss account*" OR "ESG" OR "Consensus analysis" OR "Natural Capital Accounting" OR "SOLVES" OR "inclusive valuation" OR "integrated model*" OR "participatory decision*" OR "Deliberative integration")</p>
6	Methods_A	<p>TS = (Valuation OR WTP OR "willingness to pay" OR "willingness to accept" OR WTA OR "preference assessment" OR "preference*" OR "benefit transfer*" OR "value transfer*" OR "non-monetary valuation" OR "monetary valuation" OR "elicitation method*" OR "value elicitation" OR PA-BAT OR "Trade-offs")</p>

7	Methods_B	TS = ("discourse analysis" OR "stakeholder workshop*" OR "interview*" OR "questionnaire*" OR "mental model*" OR "focus group*" OR "concept mapping" OR "Q methodology" OR "Q-methodology" OR "Q study" OR "Q-study" OR "bayesian belief network*" OR BN OR BBN OR "participatory GIS" OR "PPGIS" OR "PGIS" OR "narrative method*" OR "narrative approach*")
8	Methods_Family1	TS = (ARIES OR "InVEST model*" OR "biophysical model*" OR "bio-physical model*" OR "biophysical valu*" OR "bio-physical valu*" OR "global environmental flow" OR Mapnat OR "MARXAN" OR "MEB" OR "Ecosystem service map*" OR "ES map*" OR "Ecological importance" OR "Spatial proxy model*" OR ESTIMAP OR GISCAME OR "Cultural Health Index" OR "Environmental importance" OR "POLYSCAPE" OR "ecosystem service quantification" OR "ES quantification" OR "ecosystem service modeling" OR "ES modeling" OR "service providing unit" OR "ecosystem service supply" OR "ES supply" OR "ecosystem service delivery" OR "ES delivery" OR "species richness" OR "biodiversity index" OR "species diversity" OR "ecosystem accounting")
9	Methods_Family2	TS = ("contingent valuation" OR "choice experiment*" OR "conjoint analysis" OR "random utility" OR "RUM" OR "Marginal Utility" OR "Lancaster's Characteristics demand theory" OR "Marginal rate of substitution" OR "choice model" OR "stated preferences" OR "deliberative valuation" OR "role playing game*" OR "social assessment for protected areas" OR "socio-cultural valuation" OR "expert * elicitation" OR "Afrocentric metho*" OR "Biocultural Methods" OR SAPA OR "participatory mapping" OR "social importance" OR "socio-economic importance" OR "socio-cultural importance" OR "social preferences" OR "Hypothetical policy scenario" OR "Willingness to pay" OR "Willingness to accept" OR "Compensation" OR " Nonmarket valuation survey" OR "Individual welfare change" OR "Equivalent variation of welfare" OR "Compensatory variation of welfare" OR "Multiattribute model*" OR "multi-attribute model" OR "Discrete choice modelling" OR " Final mixture model" OR "Latent Class Model" OR "LCM" OR "Random Parameter Logit Model" OR RPLM OR "Mixed Logit Model" OR " alternative specific conditional logit")
10	Methods_Family3	TS = (hedonic OR "travel cost" OR "cost-based" OR "cost-effectiveness" OR "production function" OR "shadow pric*" OR "Health valuation" OR "Photo Elicitation" OR "Photo-Elicitation" OR "replacement cost*" OR "averting behavior" OR "economic importance" OR "livelihood assess*" OR "market price*" OR "market valu*" OR "time use" OR "mitigating cost*" OR "preventive expenditure*", OR "cost of illness" OR "participant observation" OR "observe behavior" OR "observe practice*" OR "ritua*" OR "ceremon*")
11	Methods_Family4	TS = ("cost-benefit" OR "cost benefit" OR "benefit cost" OR "benefit-cost" OR "MCA" OR "multicriteria analysis" OR "MCDA" OR "multicriteria decision analysis" OR "integrated valuation" OR "deliberative decision making" OR "business accounting" OR "corporate accounting" OR "profit and loss account*" OR ESG OR "Consensus analysis" OR "Deliberative * integration" OR "Natural Capital Accounting" OR "SolVES" OR "inclusive valuation" OR "integrated model*" OR "participatory decision*" OR "Deliberative integration")
12	DECISION MAKING = #12 = #13 OR #14 OR #15	TS=("provide information" OR "give information" OR "value formation" OR "value affirmation" OR "value expression" OR "value articulation" OR advoca* OR legitimat* OR "awareness raising" OR evaluation OR assessment* OR justif* OR "provide evidence" OR account* OR participat* OR decisive OR decision OR sustainab* OR restor* OR regulation OR conserv* OR degrad* OR negotiat* OR deliberat* OR "alternativ* formulat*" OR express* NOT "gene expression" OR prioritiz* OR prioritis* OR screen* OR rank* OR "alternative options" OR target* OR zoning OR planning OR policy OR decision* OR manage* OR extraction OR allocation OR distribution OR rights OR ownership OR licenc* OR permit* OR certif* OR quota* OR responsibilit* OR rule* OR pric* OR "price-setting" OR payment* OR charge* OR fee OR fees OR tax* OR subsidy OR subsidies OR offset* OR off-set* OR compensat* OR "damage* assessment" OR NRDA OR litigat* OR liabilit*)
13	Purpose_Informati ve	TS=("provide information" OR "give information" OR "value formation" OR "value affirmation" OR "value expression" OR "value articulation" OR advoca* OR legitimat* OR "awareness raising" OR evaluation OR assessment* OR justif* OR "provide evidence" OR account* OR participat*)
14	Purpose_Decisive	TS=(decisive OR decision OR sustainab* OR restor* OR regulation OR conserv* OR degrad* OR negotiat* OR deliberat* OR "alternativ* formulat*" OR express* NOT "gene expression" OR prioritiz* OR prioritis* OR screen* OR rank* OR "alternative options" OR target* OR zoning OR planning OR policy OR decision* OR manage* OR extraction OR allocation OR distribution OR rights OR ownership OR licenc* OR permit* OR certif* OR quota* OR responsibilit* OR rule*)
15	Purpose_Technical	TS=(pric* OR "price-setting" OR payment* OR charge* OR fee OR fees OR tax* OR subsidy OR subsidies OR offset* OR off-set* OR compensat* OR "damage* assessment" OR NRDA OR litigat* OR liabilit*)
16	Nature_Biodiversi ty	TS=(nature NOT "nature of" NOT "by its nature" OR biodiversity OR marine OR terrestrial OR forest* NOT "random forest" OR woodland* OR grassland* OR savanna* OR shrubland* OR peatland OR ecosystem* OR lake* OR river* OR sea OR ocean* OR meadow* OR heathland* OR mires OR bog* OR tundra OR biosphere OR desert* OR mountain* OR "natural resource*" OR estuar* OR fjord* OR fauna OR flora OR soil* OR "coastal waters" OR "wetland*" OR "freshwater" OR "marshland" OR "marches" OR "dryland*" OR seascape* OR landscape* OR "coast*" OR "arable land*" OR "agricultural land*" OR "natural environment*" OR "environmental resource*" OR "agroforest*" OR "agro-forest*" OR "plantation*" OR "protected areas" OR chaparral)
17	Corpus_Ch3	#1 AND #5 AND #12 AND #16
18	C1_Method A	#17 AND #6
19	C2_Method B	#17 AND #7
20	C3_Method_Family1	#17 AND #8
21	C3_Method_Family2	#17 AND #9
22	C4_Method_Family3	#17 AND #10
23	C5_Method_Family4	#17 AND #11
24	C6_Value_TYPE1	#17 AND #2
25	C7_Value_TYPE2	#17 AND #3
26	C8_Value_TYPE3	#17 AND #4
27	CORPUS_Ch4	#1 AND #5 AND #16

- **Sample extracted: 44652 papers**

The above keyword assumptions about what is a valuation application led to screen out approximately 43% of the corpus which had no method family keywords. 54% had one method keyword hit and 2% of the sample had multiple method family keyword hits. For *Chapter 4* purposes this resulted in a frame for the stratified sampling of 44652 studies (56% of the original shared corpus in **(A)**). **(R2)** describes in more detail the definition of this sample as well as the limitations of the search terms used.

Stage 3. Stratified random sampling of Method Families and Time periods based on estimated reviewer capacity.

Treatment applied: The sample was stratified based on method family and study year to provide an equal probability of representing a method family and a period. A stratified random sample over method family and year was conducted in order to have equal probability of method and year categories, and an estimated 84 studies for each of the expected 26 reviewers. Sample selection was carried out twice (June 10 and June 13) to compensate for a number of papers being screened out (see stage 4.1). This resulted in a total stratified sample of 3895 unique records (2096 + 1799). Further details of this process can be found in **(R2)**.

The assumptions about what is a valuation application resulted in a frame for the stratified sampling of 44652 papers (stage 2). In this sample family keywords were distributed as follows:

Table 2. Method family as proportion of the corpus

strata_methods	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
-----+-----			
biophysical(TS20)	31,737	70.59	70.59
integrating(TS23)	3,211	7.14	77.73
multi-method	1,537	3.42	81.15
revealed(TS22)	3,576	7.95	89.11
stated(TS21)	4,898	10.89	100.00
-----+-----			
Total	44,959	100.00	

Study year was missing from some records. Thus the sample study year was stratified as shown in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Publication year as proportion of the corpus

Categories	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
of PY			
-----+-----			
<= 2000	2,616	5.86	5.86
(2000 2005]	3,980	8.91	14.77
(2005 2010)	6,181	13.84	28.61
[2010 2015)	12,111	27.12	55.74
>= 2015	19,764	44.26	100.00
-----+-----			
Total	44,652	100.00	

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Definition of the sample of papers to be used in *Chapter 4*
- **Search language:** English
- **Sample estimated:** 3895 papers

Stage 4.1. Manual screening by study coordinators to reduce reviewing burden of non ES non-valuation studies

Treatment applied: Manual inspection showed that a large number of papers were still out of scope. This included papers on e.g., microbiological research. Papers were therefore manually screened by the three project leaders in order to identify those within the scope of the review and reduce reviewer time spent classifying out of scope papers.

Criteria for screening of papers can be found in document **(R3)**, but the general logic behind was to screen out papers based on their titles and abstracts considering the following aspects:

- If the paper does not reflect a valuation application or an environmental policy application - Screen out
- If the paper is not about ecosystem services or nature's contributions to people - Screen out
- Papers that do not link Drivers - Pressure - State with Impact - Response - Screen out

All papers submitted to reviewers were screened by 2 or 3 project leaders. Studies where at least 1 project leader considered the study in scope were kept. Studies were only excluded if both or all three project leaders considered it out of scope. Screening was carried out in two rounds (June 10th, and June 13th) by three experts applying these criteria. Screening was carried out for both the stratified samples. This resulted in a screened sample distributed to reviewers of 2023 unique studies distributed in two batches (1215+808).

- **Sample extracted:** 2023 papers

Stage 4.2 Supplemental stratified sample distributed without manual screening to assign additional papers due to large proportion of non-ES non-valuation papers in assigned samples.

A third sub-sample of papers was distributed to reviewers who had exhausted their initial assignment of papers. This third batch of papers were not pre-screened by the project leaders due to unavailability during summer leave. Papers were assigned from this batch to complete reviewer quotas. They were not fully reviewed, because the review was terminated when reviewers reached their quotas or had run out of time to work on the review.

Stage 5. Review of papers

Twenty-six reviewers were recruited to participate in the systematic review in May 2020. They were composed of 19 unpaid M.Sc. students (designated contributing authors), three other contributing authors, two fellows for the values assessment and one lead author for the values assessment. Two training workshops were carried out online in May - June 2020 by study coordinators. Reviews were carried out from June 10th to end August 2020.

Treatment applied: Selected papers were reviewed by the 26 reviewers - contributing authors and authors of the assessment - to classify them according to the rules contained in **(R4)**. Reviewers used a google form to code papers based on the following general topics:

- Valuation paper: Whether a paper was or not a valuation paper on ecosystem services / nature's contributions to people.
- Uptake paper: Whether valuation was intended for uptake or taken up in decision-making.
- Purpose of uptake: Whether valuation had an informative, decisive or technical purpose in decision making.

During the review process project leaders monitored and resolved reviewers coding questions.

- The final **sample size** coded by reviewers was N=1900 **(B)**.
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_4.4_31.08.2020_(B).csv

Stage 6. Manual validation of documented uptake studies by project leaders.

Identification of valuation documented uptake studies lies at the core of the uptake review. 178 papers (9.4%) out 1900 coded papers were identified by reviewers as documented uptake.

Project leaders conducted an extra validation check of all these 178 studies coded as “documented uptake” by reviewers. The process of validation of uptake studies was set up to ensure all uptake papers in document **(B)** were indeed “uptake” cases as defined in **(R4)** and review their purpose.

Project leaders divided the 178 studies between for validation. They found a substantial number of “false positives” in the reviewers’ work, relative to their own assessment of the protocol. There was also discrepancy between study coordinators of uptake in their 3 samples, with 20%, 24% and 50% of the 178 reviewer-identified uptake studies being validated as uptake studies by the three project leaders, respectively. Across all 178 studies, 66 were confirmed to be uptake, or 37% of uptake. The false positive rate for uptake is therefore 67%. Statistical findings of uptake in the main body of the report are therefore qualified as a range using this correction factor.

The main project leader also reviewed a subsample (N=54) to check for correspondence in coding of valuation purposes. We found a correspondence rate of informative (72%), Decisive (52%) and Technical (92%). Statistical findings in the main body of the report should be qualified by this coding uncertainty.

Quantifying uncertainty in uptake coding

The proportion of uptake depends on whether the denominator is taken as the total number of studies reviewed (N=1900) or the number of valuation applications (N=1123). In order to compare with other systematic reviews in the literature (e.g. Laurans et al. 2013) the denominator must be clarified. Without further clarification the upper uptake uncertainty range for documented uptake is [9.4% (Ns=178/N=1900), 15.7% (Ns=178/N=1123)]. Applying the correction factor of 37% found in the validation above, a lower bound uptake is [3.5% (Ns=66/N=1900) , 5.9% (Ns=66/N=1123)].

CAs were a mix of student graduates and experienced researchers, mainly classifying papers outside their domain of expertise. Based on our validation we conclude that documented uptake among studies valuing ES/NCP may lie in a range of between an upper estimate of <15.7%/ 9.4%>, and a lower estimate of 3.6%. By comparison Laurans et al. (2013) found that only 2% of valuation studies reviewed in Ecological Economics documented use. Despite classification uncertainty among ‘non-expert’ CA reviewers, we can still conclude that a small minority of valuation studies document how they are taken up by stakeholders. Looking across multiple valuation methods, and 7 years after Laurans blindspot study there are weak indications of improvement in uptake documentation.

We note that Chapters 3 & 4 used the same protocol for identifying uptake studies, and that confidence levels should be checked against those of Chapter 3 methods review.

Reviewer consistency in coding uptake and purpose

137 of the 1900 papers were also duplicated to review screening consistency among reviewers.

Stage 7. Narrative analysis of validated uptake studies

From stage 6, 66 papers were identified as documented uptake after validation.

Treatment applied: A narrative analysis was conducted in the main body of the report of a selection of these studies.

Analysis of the data. Statistical analysis: A descriptive statistical analysis was conducted for data in document (A)², and for the 66 papers in this sample, to describe general trends, means and relative averages.

There were two components to this analysis:

- Uptake review and validation results from Stage 6.
- Study date, method family and country variables from document (A).

Frequencies and sample proportions for variables (Unvalidated review)

1) Descriptive statistics summarising the survey results

Frequencies and sample proportions for variables in Unvalidated review

- Q4 uptake
- Q6 informative
- Q7 informative type
- Q8 decisive
- Q9 decisive type
- Q13 technical
- Q14 technical type

Frequencies and sample proportions for variables in Validated review

- Validated uptake total
- Validated uptake informative
- Validated uptake decisive
- Validated uptake technical

2) Geographical representation of the data

Maps were created to provide a graphical representation of the literature corpus, valuation uptake sample and analyse spatial correlations.³

The following correlation matrix (Pearssons corr.coef) looks at correlations between IPBES core indicators and study and affiliation frequency for only the last decade since 2010.

² Presented in Valuation Atlas (10.5281/zenodo.6468906)

³ Presented in Valuation Atlas (10.5281/zenodo.6468906)

Figure 1. Correlation matrix for studies in the corpus since 2010

Figure 2. Correlation matrix for studies since 2010 in the valuation uptake review

Table 4. Number of observations per Pearson's correlation coefficient

N observations	post 2010		Documened uptake	Informative purpose	Decisive purpose	Technical purpose
	ES/NCP valuation	ES/NCP valuation				
Human Development Index 2018	113	84	106	95	85	30
Learning_outcomes 2015	69	52	65	58	53	25
Gross Domestic Product (GDP) 2018	116	85	109	98	87	32
Corruption perception index 2018	111	82	104	95	83	30
GDP per capita	116	85	109	98	87	32
Population per km2	117	85	110	98	88	33
Forest Area under FSC certification	71	59	67	60	56	24
Biodiversity Habitat Index	103	79	97	85	79	30
Biodiversity Intactness Index	115	86	108	95	87	31
Biocapacity per capita	109	81	102	91	82	31
Ecological Footprint per capita	109	81	102	91	82	31
Forest area	116	86	109	96	88	32
Water Footprint	112	84	105	94	85	30
Inland Fishery Production	115	85	108	96	87	32
Marine Trophic Index (1950)	68	46	64	58	52	18
Nitrogen Fertilizers	114	83	107	96	86	32
Nitrogen Use Efficiency (%)	96	76	92	84	76	28
Percentage protected	117	86	110	97	88	32
Percentage of undernourished people	108	83	101	90	82	29
Local Breeds at risk of extinction	113	84	106	95	86	31
PA of Key Biodiversity Areas Coverage (%)	99	74	94	83	76	28
Protected area management effectiveness	102	77	96	85	77	27
Protected Area Connectedness Index	118	86	111	98	89	33
Species Habitat Index	112	83	105	93	86	31
Species Protection Index (%)	118	86	111	98	89	33
Species Status Information Index	116	86	109	96	88	32
Total Wood Removals	114	84	107	95	87	32
Trends in forest extent	114	85	107	94	86	31
Nitrogen Deposition Trends	111	83	104	92	86	31
Trends in Pesticides Use	64	52	62	55	48	18

Table 5. Significance of Pearson's correlation coefficients - valuation uptake and purposes with development and IPBES core indicators

	ES/NCP valuation	ES/NCP valuation	Documened uptake	Informative purpose	Decisive purpose	Technical purpose
Significance (p<0.01 in red)						
Human Development Index 2018	0,001	0,003	0,002	0,003	0,000	0,305
Learning_outcomes 2015	0,172	0,090	0,168	0,267	0,159	0,486
Gross Domestic Product (GDP) 2018	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Corruption perception index 2018	0,002	0,009	0,004	0,014	0,001	0,907
GDP per capita	0,004	0,006	0,002	0,013	0,000	0,774
Population per km2	0,598	0,002	0,000	0,001	0,004	0,468
Forest Area under FSC certification	0,276	0,305	0,182	0,136	0,439	0,829
Biodiversity Habitat Index	0,108	0,187	0,155	0,238	0,138	0,114
Biodiversity Intactness Index	0,001	0,000	0,002	0,007	0,000	0,123
Biocapacity per capita	0,931	0,020	0,925	0,498	0,882	0,446
Ecological Footprint per capita	0,002	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,297
Forest area	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,001
Water Footprint	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Inland Fishery Production	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,000
Marine Trophic Index (1950)	0,703	0,578	0,755	0,852	0,343	0,053
Nitrogen Fertilizers	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Nitrogen Use Efficiency (%)	0,898	0,752	0,941	0,965	0,609	0,302
Percentage protected	0,887	0,702	0,816	0,716	0,692	0,583
Percentage of undernourished people	0,088	0,087	0,090	0,084	0,100	0,182
Local Breeds at risk of extinction	0,330	0,727	0,337	0,452	0,203	0,744
PA of Key Biodiversity Areas Coverage (%)	0,823	0,775	0,797	0,981	0,514	0,443
Protected area management effectiveness	0,010	0,012	0,009	0,034	0,005	0,366
Protected Area Connectedness Index	0,087	0,014	0,047	0,013	0,244	0,085
Species Habitat Index	0,829	0,581	0,661	0,663	0,569	0,550
Species Protection Index (%)	0,226	0,476	0,241	0,314	0,101	0,671
Species Status Information Index	0,219	0,622	0,149	0,367	0,056	0,371
Total Wood Removals	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Trends in forest extent	0,223	0,810	0,445	0,690	0,914	0,624
Nitrogen Deposition Trends	0,134	0,365	0,139	0,216	0,039	0,451
Trends in Pesticides Use	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,002	0,000

Table 6. Pearson's correlation coefficients - valuation uptake and purposes with development and IPBES core indicators

	ES/NCP valuation	post 2010 ES/NCP valuation	Documened uptake	Informative purpose	Decisive purpose	Technical purpose
Pearssons correlation coefficient						
Human Development Index 2018	0,30	0,32	0,30	0,30	0,37	0,19
Learning_outcomes 2015	0,17	0,24	0,17	0,15	0,20	0,15
Gross Domestic Product (GDP) 2018	0,71	0,74	0,71	0,74	0,65	0,74
Corruption perception index 2018	0,29	0,29	0,28	0,25	0,35	0,02
GDP per capita	0,27	0,29	0,29	0,25	0,38	0,05
Population per km2	0,05	0,33	0,37	0,34	0,31	0,13
Forest Area under FSC certification	0,13	0,14	0,17	0,19	0,11	0,05
Biodiversity Habitat Index	0,16	0,15	0,15	0,13	0,17	0,29
Biodiversity Intactness Index	0,30	0,39	0,30	0,27	0,42	0,28
Biocapacity per capita	0,01	0,26	0,01	0,07	0,02	0,14
Ecological Footprint per capita	0,29	0,42	0,39	0,36	0,44	0,19
Forest area	0,35	0,54	0,56	0,62	0,44	0,56
Water Footprint	0,58	0,61	0,58	0,63	0,46	0,77
Inland Fishery Production	0,41	0,49	0,43	0,48	0,35	0,65
Marine Trophic Index (1950)	0,05	0,08	0,04	0,02	0,13	0,46
Nitrogen Fertilizers	0,60	0,71	0,62	0,67	0,51	0,78
Nitrogen Use Efficiency (%)	0,01	0,04	0,01	0,00	0,06	0,20
Percentage protected	0,01	0,04	0,02	0,04	0,04	0,10
Percentage of undernourished people	0,16	0,19	0,17	0,18	0,18	0,25
Local Breeds at risk of extinction	0,09	0,04	0,09	0,08	0,14	0,06
PA of Key Biodiversity Areas Coverage (%)	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,00	0,08	0,15
Protected area management effectiveness	0,25	0,29	0,27	0,23	0,32	0,18
Protected Area Connectedness Index	0,16	0,26	0,19	0,25	0,12	0,30
Species Habitat Index	0,02	0,06	0,04	0,05	0,06	0,11
Species Protection Index (%)	0,11	0,08	0,11	0,10	0,17	0,08
Species Status Information Index	0,11	0,05	0,14	0,09	0,20	0,16
Total Wood Removals	0,65	0,65	0,67	0,72	0,55	0,70
Trends in forest extent	0,11	0,03	0,07	0,04	0,01	0,09
Nitrogen Deposition Trends	0,14	0,10	0,15	0,13	0,22	0,14
Trends in Pesticides Use	0,60	0,80	0,66	0,73	0,44	0,80

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.4_06.05.2020_(A)	csv	326.3 MB	Original sample of 79040 papers, including the identification of countries, IPBES regions and subregions and terms from within the search terms found in titles, abstracts of keywords
B	IPBES_VA_4.4_31.08.2020_(B)	csv	476 KB	Sample coded by reviewers (1900 papers)
R1	IPBES_VA_4.4_06.05.2020_(R1)	txt	140 KB	Search terms for collecting the corpus of 79040 papers in .txt format
R1	IPBES_VA_4.4_06.05.2020_(R1)	wos	139 KB	Search terms for collecting the corpus of 79040 papers in .wos format
R2	IPBES_VA_4.4_10.06.2020_(R2)	pdf	234 KB	Documentation of the stratified sample definition (stages 2 and 3)
R3	IPBES_VA_4.4_10.06.2020_(R3)	pdf	117 KB	Criteria for screening out papers
R4	IPBES_VA_4.4_10.06.2020_(R4)	pdf	453 KB	Rules for studies review